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HISTORICAL PECULIARITIES OF SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF PEOPLE WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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Abstract

The main aim was to study and analyze historical and psychological and pedagogical aspects of the development of children with cerebral palsy, in particular - to study the medical and physical characteristics (clinical features), the psychological well-being of children, and the educational approaches and problems (pedagogy) associated with CP. Detailed information is collected on the type and severity of CP, associated symptomatology; information on educational interventions, support services and challenges faced by children with cerebral palsy in educational settings. The paper discusses the possible causes of CP, allowing the disease to be categorized by its manifestations and possibly prevented. CP is a multifactorial disorder, but despite a long history of research in the scientific community, there is no consensus on the predominant impact of CP on children's socialisation and development. A child with CP may have problems with speech motor skills. There is a problem of early diagnosis and, as a consequence, the beginning of treatment measures, which, in turn, largely determines the course of the disease.

Keywords: cerebral palsy (CP), types of paralysis, rehabilitation, development, disease, brain.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cerebral palsy (CP) is a group of movement disorders that appear in early childhood. "Cerebral" means having to do with the brain. Paralysis means weakness or problems using muscles. Signs and symptoms vary from person to person and over time, but include poor coordination, muscle stiffness, muscle weakness and tremors. There may be problems with sensation, vision, hearing and speech [1]. Often children with cerebral palsy are developmentally delayed in rolling over, sitting up, crawling and walking compared to healthy children their age. The CP clinic may be accompanied by seizures and cognitive problems, occurring in about one-third of CP patients. Although symptoms may become more prominent during the first few years of life, the underlying problems do not resolve over time [2].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study uses a historical review approach to trace the understanding and classification of cerebral palsy over the years. Primary sources, including ancient Greek medical texts, early medical publications, and the prolific work of key figures in CP research such as William John Little, William Osler, Sigmund Freud, Winthrop Phelps, and Andras Peto, form the basis of this study. In addition, contemporary perspectives are examined through the lens of the Gross Motor Function Classification System (GMFCS) introduced by Robert Palisano in 1997 and its subsequent revisions in 2007. The paper synthesizes information from various sources to provide a comprehensive overview of the historical evolution and classification of CP.

III. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Cerebral palsy has affected people since ancient times. The medical literature of the ancient Greeks discusses paralysis and weakness of the arms and legs. The works of the school of Hippocrates (460-370 BC) and, in particular, the manuscript "On Sacred Disease" describe a group of problems that fits very well with the modern understanding of CP [3].

The modern understanding of CP as the result of brain problems began in the first decades of the 19th century with a series of publications on brain abnormalities by Johann Christian Reil, Claude François Lallemand, and Philippe Pinel. Later doctors used this research to link problems in the brain to specific symptoms. The English surgeon William John Little (1810-1894) was the first to study CP in detail. In his doctoral thesis, he stated that CP was the result of a problem at the time of birth. One of the surgeon's more significant contributions is recognised as a course of published lectures entitled "On the Nature and Treatment of Deformities of the Human Body." (1843). By 1861 Little was ready to present the first definition of cerebral palsy to the London Midwifery Society. He later identified difficult labor, preterm birth and perinatal asphyxia, among others, as risk factors. The spastic form of CP diplegia became known to the masses as Little's disease. Around the same time, a German surgeon also worked on cerebral palsy and distinguished it from poliomyelitis. In the 1880s, the British neurologist William Gowers, building on Little's work, linked paralysis in newborns to difficult labour. He called the problem "paralysis at birth" and divided paralysis into two types: peripheral and cerebral [4-7].

Working in the United States in the 1880s, Canadian-born physician William Osler (1849-1919) studied dozens of cases of CP to further classify the disorders by the localization of problems in the body and by root cause. Osler made further observations linking problems during childbirth to CP and concluded that problems causing bleeding within the brain were probably the underlying cause. Osler suspected polyoencephalitis as an infectious cause. It is due to his scientific work that we have the familiar name for this disease. The specific term comes from the book "Infantile Cerebral Palsy" (1887) [8]. Before turning to psychiatry, the Austrian neurologist Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) further refined the classification of the disorder. He created a system that is still in use today. Freud's system divides the causes of the disorder into problems present at birth, problems that develop during birth, and problems after birth. Freud also made a rough correlation between the localization of the problem within the brain and the location of the affected limbs on the body and documented a big part of movement disorders [9].

Also among the pioneers in the field of cerebral palsy research are a couple Goldenson. Leonard and Isabelle had a very traumatic experience with the condition. Their firstborn child was born with cerebral palsy, and the loving parents devoted all their energies to learning about the nuances of the condition. However, their endeavors did not meet with a positive outcome. The Goldensons' daughter died of complications at the age of 29. In 1950, the Goldenson couple co-founded the United Cerebral Palsy Association. Today, the health organization studying this issue is the 5th largest within the USA. In 1994, Harvard Medical School named a research building after the couple - the Isabelle and Leonard Goldenson Biometric Research Centre.

This honor is fully justified, the couple's efforts have donated more than 60 million to neurological research, and they have managed to attract NASA engineers to their charitable causes, inspiring the design of a lightweight wheelchair [10]. Another key person in publicizing CP has been writer and activist Marie Killilea. The woman wrote two New York Times bestsellers based on the true story of her daughter, who was born with cerebral palsy. "Karen" and "With Love Karen" are books that for the first time address advocacy for parents of children with special needs. Talking about the progression of cerebral palsy study one cannot fail to mention a doctor like Winthrop Phelps and his services in this segment. In 1937, he founded the first of its kind Institute of Paediatric Rehabilitation. The institution specialized in the treatment and care of children with cerebral palsy [11].

In 1932, Phelps published the first scientific article in the 20th century on the subject of this diagnosis. In it, he argued that not all children have cognitive impairment, instead only their musculoskeletal system is affected. The doctor also noted, the symptoms of people with CP could be minimal. Such people can well become full members of a productive society and acquire the necessary degree of socialization. In 1947, Dr. Winthrop, along with the efforts of five other physicians working with SR patients, founded the American Academy of Cerebral Palsy. He was elected the first president of the organization.

More than 70 years later, the association was renamed the American Academy of Cerebral Palsy and Developmental Medicine (AAPDM), which is still in existence today [11, 12].

One of the initiatives aimed at summarizing and further developing current views on CP was the creation of the Little Club, initiated by R. MacKeith and P Polani in 1957, the Little Club. Two years later, they published a Memorandum on the classification and terminology of cerebral palsy. According to the definition of the Little Club' cerebral palsy is a non-progressive brain lesion that appears in the early years of life with impairments of movement and body position. These impairments resulting from impaired brain development' are non-progressive but modifiable [4-7].

In the recent future, scientists of different nationalities have put forward different interpretations of the concept of cerebral palsy. Professor Ksenia Aleksandrovna Semenovna, a leading neurologist in the field of cerebral palsy and head of the largest center for patients in the post-Soviet space, offers a definition according to which cerebral palsy unites a group of clinical syndromes that manifest themselves as a result of brain damage at different stages of orthogenesis. The International Workshop on the Definition and Classification of Cerebral Palsy (Maryland, USA, July 2004) was an important event that led to the development of modern views on cerebral palsy [13].

CP is nowadays defined as "a group of permanent developmental disorders of movement and posture causing activity limitation that are associated with non-progressive abnormalities originating in the developing fetal or infant brain" [14, P. 19]. It is generally believed that muscle contractions in people with cerebral palsy are due to over activity. Importance in modern society is given to the socialization of children with CP studying this problem will help to become more familiar with this disease and, accordingly, better understand the possible ways of accepting special people in their environment and society as a whole.

The aim of our study was to investigate and analyze the clinical-psychological and pedagogical features of the development of children with CP.

Infantile cerebral palsy is characterized by abnormal muscle tone, reflexes or motor development and coordination. The neurological lesion is primary and permanent, whereas orthopaedic manifestations are secondary and progressive. In cerebral palsy, uneven growth of musculotendinous units and bone eventually leads to bone and joint deformities [15]. Hungarian physical rehabilitation specialist András Pető developed a system for teaching walking and other basic movements to children with CP. Pető's system became the basis for conductive learning, which is widely used today for children with CP [5, 16].

Robert Palisano et al. (1997) introduced the International Classification of Impairments, Disabilities, and Handicaps (ICIDH) as an improvement over the previous crude assessment of limitation as mild, moderate, or severe. The ICIDH limitation is assessed on the basis of observed mastery of specific basic mobility skills such as sitting, standing and walking, and takes into account the level of dependence on aids such as wheelchairs or walkers [17].

CP and its connection with children's education possibility

Understanding information about cerebral palsy (CP) and connected symptoms, especially deformities and motor dysfunctions, is crucial for educators and educationalists. The impact of cerebral palsy on a child's ability to acquire knowledge is multifaceted and requires an individualized approach to education [18]. Here are some links between the manifestation and diagnostic features of CP and educational attainment:

▶ *Motor problems and learning style adaptation*

- Children with CP may exhibit a variety of gait disturbances: tiptoe or scissor gait. This can affect children's mobility and their physical interaction with the environment. Educators should be aware of these problems and create an environment that accommodates different movement patterns.

- Understanding the continuum of motor dysfunction in cerebral palsy helps teachers to recognize different degrees of impairment. Adapting teaching strategies to accommodate different levels of motor function ensures that every child can participate effectively in learning activities [19].

There are three main classifications of CP according to movement disorders: spastic, ataxic and dyskinetic. In addition, there is a mixed type, which shows a combination of features of the other types.

Deformities in general and static deformities in particular (joint contractures) cause increasing gait difficulties in the form of tiptoe gait due to Achilles tendon strain and scissor gait due to high adductor muscle strain. These gait patterns are among the most common gait disorders in children with cerebral palsy. However, the orthopaedic manifestations of CP are varied. In addition, squatting gait (gait with excessive knee flexion) is common among children who are able to walk. Although most people with CP have problems with increased muscle tone, some have normal or decreased muscle tone [20, 21].

▶ *Orthopaedic manifestations and accessibility of classes*

- Joint deformities and contractures can affect a child's posture and comfort in traditional classroom settings. Educators should consider providing ergonomic seating, assistive devices, or modifications to the physical learning environment [22].

Children born with severe cerebral palsy often have abnormal posture; their bodies may be either very flexible or very stiff. Children born with cerebral palsy do not show symptoms immediately [21, 22].

▶ *Early detection and stages of development*

- Recognizing the signs of CP, which often become evident between 6 and 9 months of age, allows educators to intervene early. Early intervention programs and specialized educational strategies can be implemented to support the developmental needs of children with CP [23].

▶ *Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) and specialized support*

- Children with CP may have a range of abilities and challenges. Developing personalized IEPs that address specific motor and cognitive needs ensures that educational goals are achievable and meaningful for each child [24].

▶ *Communication strategies*

- Some children with CP may find it difficult to communicate and educators should be prepared to use alternative methods of communication such as complementary and alternative communication (CAC) systems [25].

▶ *Co-operation with related specialists*

- Collaboration with physiotherapists, occupational therapists and other allied professionals is crucial. Educators should work in tandem with these professionals to implement recommended strategies and exercises that support the child's physical development.

Thus, integrating cerebral palsy information with pedagogy involves recognizing the diverse challenges faced by these children and implementing individualized educational strategies to meet their unique needs [26].

Cognitive disorders connected with CP

Salivation is common among children with cerebral palsy and can have a variety of consequences including social rejection, speech impairment, damage to clothes and books, and oral infections [1].

A child with cerebral palsy may have problems with speech motor skills. We use a complex combination of muscles in the face, throat, neck and other parts of the body to speak. Childhood cerebral palsy can affect the part of the brain responsible for speech [27].

Speech and language disorders associated with cerebral palsy include:

Articulation disorders: patients may have poor oral-motor control and muscle weakness of the face and throat.

Fluency disorders: interruptions such as stuttering disrupt the flow of speech.

Voice disorders: uneven pitch and voice quality, make it difficult for children to communicate.

Expressive disorders: difficulty in selecting words to convey ideas [28].

Prevalence of symptoms of lower urinary tract dysfunction and their relationship with educational characteristics

On average, 55.5% of people with cerebral palsy experience lower urinary tract symptoms, more often problems with over accumulation than problems with urination. Those with urinary problems and pelvic floor hyperactivity may worsen in adulthood and experience upper urinary tract dysfunction. The prevalence of symptoms of lower urinary tract dysfunction (SLUTD) in individuals with CP has significant implications for educational characteristics and requires thoughtful consideration by educators [29, 30]. Such symptoms can significantly impact children's socialisation and learning.

► *Physical comfort and concentration in the classroom*

- Students with CP who experience SLUTD, especially those associated with excessive urine accumulation, may experience physical discomfort. Teachers should be aware of these problems and create an environment that allows for movement or breaks when necessary to alleviate discomfort and maintain concentration during class.

► *Scheduled breaks and availability*

- People with cerebral palsy and urinary symptoms may require scheduled breaks or access to appropriate facilities. Teachers should work with health professionals, parents and students themselves to develop a support plan that allows for timely toilet breaks without disrupting the learning environment.

► *Awareness and understanding*

- Educators need to be aware of the prevalence of SLUTD in individuals with cerebral palsy to promote understanding and empathy.

► *Individual accommodation*

- If a student experiences a worsening of urinary symptoms or pelvic floor hyperactivity in adulthood, individualized adjustments may be required. This may include flexible scheduling, access to assistive devices, or changes to the physical learning environment.

► *Communication with health care professionals*

- Regular communication with health care professionals involved in the treatment of students with CP is crucial. This co-operation ensures that teachers are informed of any changes in the students' condition.

► *Inclusive physical education*

- Consideration should be given to including pupils with CP in physical education sessions. Teachers should work with physiotherapists and adapt physical activity to meet the needs and abilities of students.

► *Promotion of self-defense*

- Teachers can empower students with cerebral palsy to advocate for their own needs, including those related to urinary symptoms. Teaching self-defence skills helps students to communicate their demands and promotes a sense of independence in managing their health.

► *Understanding the potential impact on concentration*

- By understanding that urinary symptoms may distract students or cause discomfort, teachers can implement strategies to minimise disruption to concentration.

Thus, incorporating awareness of urinary symptoms associated with cerebral palsy into educational planning enables teachers to create an inclusive and supportive learning environment [31, 32].

Socialization of patients with CP

A movement disorder can have a significant impact on socialisation and educational opportunities for people.

Peer interaction. Individuals with movement disorders may experience problems with motor coordination, which affects their ability to participate in physical activities and play with peers [5].

Communication. Some movement disorders can also affect speech or make it difficult to communicate. This can lead to difficulties in expressing yourself and communicating

Stigma and acceptance. Children with noticeable motor impairments may face stigma or discrimination from their peers, which affects their social acceptance. Educators play a critical role in creating an inclusive environment that promotes understanding and acceptance among students. In general education settings, educators may need to implement adaptations and accommodations to support a student's learning needs. This may include providing assistive technology, modifying assignments, or additional time for physical movement tasks [19, 26, 33].

Physical challenges in the classroom. Motor impairments can affect a student's ability to navigate the physical environment of a typical classroom. For example, fine motor difficulties can affect tasks such as writing or using classroom tools, impacting academic performance. Teachers must be trained to recognise and understand the specific problems associated with this diagnosis [19].

Special education for students with CP

Special education of students with CP involves a number of inclusive features. These include:

Individual Education Plans (IEPs). Students with motor impairments may qualify to form an IEP. This plan outlines specific goals, accommodations, and support services tailored to the student's needs [24].

Therapeutic interventions. Specific training may include additional support from occupational therapists, physiotherapists or other professionals who can address specific movement problems [26].

Social skills development. Special education programmes often include social skills development. This can be particularly helpful for people with movement disorders who may face social challenges [34, 35].

IV. CONCLUSION

A movement disorder can have wide-ranging effects on socialization and education. This emphasises the importance of creating inclusive environments, raising awareness, providing appropriate accommodations and offering individualized support to ensure that people with movement disorders have equal opportunities for social interaction and education.

Connecting CP with pedagogy involves a holistic approach that addresses the diverse needs of students with this condition. By adopting inclusive practices, using assistive technology and collaborating with support services, teachers can create an environment that supports the academic and social success of students with cerebral palsy. CP can be conjugated with cognitive impairment affecting various aspects of intellectual functioning. The extent and nature of cognitive problems can vary widely among individuals with CP. It is important for educators and educationalists to recognize these potential cognitive consequences and adapt educational strategies accordingly.

Addressing CP-related cognitive impairment in the context of pedagogy requires a personalized and flexible approach. By recognizing the individual strengths and challenges of each student, teachers can create inclusive learning environments that maximize the cognitive development and academic success of people with CP. Addressing the impact of motor impairment on socialization and education requires a holistic and collaborative approach. By creating inclusive environments, introducing appropriate accommodations and fostering peer understanding, teachers can play a key role in ensuring that people with motor impairments are able to thrive socially and academically.

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ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ АДАПТАЦИИ ЛЮДЕЙ С ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНЫМ ПАРАЛИЧОМ

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Аннотация

Основной целью исследования было изучение и анализ исторических и психолого-педагогических аспектов развития детей с ДЦП, в частности изучение медицинских и физических характеристик (клинические особенности), психологического благополучия детей, образовательных подходов и проблем (педагогика), связанных с ДЦП. Собирается подробная информация о типе и тяжести ЦП, сопутствующей симптоматике; информация об образовательных вмешательствах, службах поддержки и проблемах, с которыми сталкиваются дети с ДЦП в образовательных учреждениях. В статье рассматриваются возможные причины ЦП, что позволяет классифицировать заболевание по его проявлениям и, возможно, предотвратить его. ДЦП - многофакторное заболевание, но, несмотря на длительную историю исследований в научном сообществе, нет единого мнения о преимущественном влиянии ДЦП на социализацию и развитие детей. У ребенка с ЦП могут быть проблемы с речевыми двигательными навыками. Существует проблема ранней диагностики и, как следствие, начала лечебных мероприятий, что, в свою очередь, во многом определяет течение заболевания.

Ключевые слова: детский церебральный паралич (ДЦП), типы параличей, реабилитация, развитие, заболевание, мозг.

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